

Original research

Towards improved methodology to measure the uptake of mammography in populations using insurance claims: a case study from Delaware, USA

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Running Head: Adjusting Mammography Claims due to Underreporting

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Abstract

Background: Quantifying the uptake of screening mammography at a population level is challenged by suboptimal surveillance data. Insurance claims represent a potentially useful data source, however, claims data can be limited by underreporting. Using a quantitative bias analysis framework, we demonstrate an approach for dealing with imperfect sensitivity in an insurance claims database.

Methods: Insurance claims were obtained at the census tract level for screening mammography for the State of Delaware for 2019 and 2022. A measurement model related the observed uptake of mammography to the truth via two approaches: 1) the total number of medical claims, and 2) proportion of government funded health insurance. We then modeled how uptake of mammography predicts invasive breast cancer incidence and stage at diagnosis in Delaware.

Results: During the year 2022 and based on the observed measure, the statewide averaged uptake was 176 mammograms per 1,000 women aged 40 and above. This figure increased to a median of 234 mammograms per 1,000 women (95% simulation interval: 230, 239) following adjustment. Each additional 1,000 mammograms predicted an increase of 126 breast cancer cases using the observed data (95% confidence interval: 112, 140), whereas following adjustment, this number was attenuated to 77 cases (95% simulation interval: 63, 90). Mammography uptake was less predictive of more advanced stage disease following adjustment, in line with our hypothesis.

Conclusions: When working with administrative datasets for measuring the uptake of screening mammography in a population, researchers and healthcare administrators should account for potential underreporting.

Key words: breast neoplasms; mammography; surveillance; bias; insurance claims

Introduction

The uptake of screening mammography in a population is an important indicator for the early detection of breast cancer to enable earlier treatment and lower mortality. The accurate measurement of this indicator at broad geographic levels is challenged by suboptimal surveillance. For example, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (BRFSS) includes self-reported questions on the receipt of screening mammography. While these data are frequently used in breast cancer research, they are problematic because of social desirability bias, over-reporting, and nonresponse and sampling error, leading to documented overestimation. One report that drew on interviews and health records estimated that 4 in 10 self-reported mammograms were overreported.¹ Another analysis found that overreporting varies across age and other demographic categories, raising concerns about bias in estimating disparities.² In addition, BRFSS data are reported for larger scale geographic areas (e.g., counties) that makes it difficult to identify high-priority communities for outreach interventions. While small area estimates are available at a more granular scale, these estimates have their limitations.³

The use of insurance claims databases may overcome the overreporting and geographic-based limitations of survey approaches, because screening mammography is a reimbursable procedure linked to a known patient residential address. However, these databases are also subject to misclassification. For example, claims databases may underestimate mammography utilization among those who self-pay, though those rates have dropped since the passage of the Affordable Care Act.⁴ Similarly, not all insurers are

mandated to report to these databases. Delaware is one such state where coverage is differential by insurer, with certain self-insured businesses or commercial insurance plans not required to report into the claims database.

Case study

Delaware leads the U.S. in late-stage breast cancer among women under the age of 50.⁵ Reasons for this are varied but may include suboptimal rates of screening mammography uptake and a higher risk population.⁶ The Delaware Health Information Network (DHIN), the first statewide health information exchange in the U.S., serves all of Delaware's hospitals and nearly all of Delaware's medical providers, and facilitates real time exchange of patients' health information. The Health Care Claims Database (HCCD), run by DHIN and legislated by the State, serves as the largest claims database in the State and covers Medicaid, Medicare Advantage, and the seven largest commercial health insurers in the State (insurers with fewer than 1,000 covered lives are not mandated to report to HCCD).⁷ One use of the HCCD is to help improve population health, which may occur via research done on its data such as to identify communities for outreach to increase uptake, provided such communities can be accurately ranked in terms of underutilization. However, since the HCCD does not cover all insurers in the State, including those without insurance, these data are known to be underreported. On the other hand, claims reported to the database are verified by the payors. Thus, we can posit that the HCCD suffers from imperfect sensitivity but likely has near-perfect specificity. At worst,

research findings may be biased if underreporting of mammography is not randomly distributed across the population, and at best, precision of these estimates is artificially higher giving false confidence in these estimates. As such, we sought to account for this underreporting via a quantitative bias analysis. If our method can improve upon the measurement of screening mammography utilization, it should be to recapitulate known, rather than biased, population-level associations between mammography uptake and breast cancer stage at diagnoses. *A priori*, we hypothesized that higher amounts of screening mammography would be associated with a greater number of total breast cancer cases (enabling earlier connection to care) but would be unrelated to later-stage cases as these cancers would be detected through other means.

Methods

Population and geography

Our work focused on census tracts in Delaware, the smallest geographic unit for which data were available. The total population of women aged 40 and older per tract, who are eligible to receive routine screening mammography and will serve as our denominator in subsequent calculations, was obtained from the 2020 American Community Survey 5-year estimates.

Mammography uptake (observed measure)

Screening mammography data were obtained for the entire State of Delaware from the HCCD on October 22, 2024, for the years 2019 and 2022, the most recent pre-COVID year and the most recent year with data available post-COVID, respectively. We specifically wanted to avoid the peak of the COVID disruptions on screening, although our primary focus was the post-COVID year 2022 (2019 results are presented in the eAppendix). These data correspond to census-tract level number of claims for unique individuals who completed screening mammography and are known to underestimate the number of women who completed screening.

Breast cancer diagnoses

Census-tract level counts of breast cancer diagnoses were obtained from the Delaware Cancer Registry on April 21, 2025. These data correspond to incident diagnoses of invasive disease between 2012 through 2021 and stratified by stage including local and late (i.e., regional or distant). We assume these data are measured without error.

Misclassification model

For a fixed time and location, the true number of women who have received screening mammograms (M_i) in the i^{th} census tract is related to the observed prevalence of reported mammograms (p_i), the number of women eligible for screening mammography (N_i), and the reporting sensitivity of the HCCD (γ_i) as shown in Eq. 1.

$$\text{Eq. 1. } M_i = N_i * p_i / \gamma_i$$

We assume there are no “false positive” claims reported, thus specificity is perfect. p_i can be described by a Beta distribution with the shape parameters $(O_i + 1, N_i - O_i + 1)$, where O_i is the observed count of reported mammograms.

DHIN estimates missing approximately 40% of medical claims data for Delaware. HCCD data tend to be the most complete for areas with a greater proportion of government funded health insurance plans, specifically Medicaid and Medicare, followed by commercial insurance, and least complete for self-insured employers and uninsured individuals. Medicare includes only Medicare Advantage as opposed to traditional Medicare fee-for-service, corresponding to approximately one third of total Medicare claims in Delaware.⁸ For each census tract, DHIN has also provided the total number of women aged 40 or greater with *any* claim in the HCCD, not just a screening mammography insurance claim. In other words, we were provided with one observed value of screening mammograms per census tract (p_i) and propose two alternatives that relate this observed value to the truth via the sensitivity parameter γ_i : one based on total number of medical claims (termed DHIN-specification) and one based on proportion of government funded health insurance (termed Census-specification).

DHIN-specification

Recognizing that the HCCD coverage can be estimated per census tract based on the total number of mammogram-eligible women who had *any* claims reported from that

tract (T_i) divided by the total population of mammogram-eligible women (N_i), it is reasonable to represent the tract-specific sensitivity γ_i as a Uniform distribution bound between $(T_i/N_i, 1)$. The lower bound of γ_i represents a situation where all screening-eligible women received mammograms, but only women with insurers reporting to DHIN were captured in the HCCD. Thus, these data provide some sense of the coverage of the HCCD in that census tract. For example, should there be 900 women with *any* insurance claim in a census tract and the American Community Survey estimates there are 1,000 women residing in that same tract, we can posit that the HCCD's coverage in that tract is at least 90%. In this example, mammography claims may range from being fully captured in the HCCD (if all eligible women whose insurers do not report to DHIN also did not receive mammograms, sensitivity $\gamma_i=1.00$) to being underestimated by 10% in the HCCD (if all eligible women whose insurers do not report to DHIN actually received mammograms, sensitivity $\gamma_i=0.90$).

Census-specification

Our second measure of a tract-specific sensitivity η_i is given in Eq. 2 and is a modification of γ_i from Eq. 1. In Eq.2, we assumed that the HCCD sensitivity increases with the census tract-specific proportion of women aged 40 and older receiving government funded health insurance (c_i).

$$\text{Eq. 2. } \eta_i = \phi_i * c_i + (\pi_i * (1 - c_i))$$

This specification required two additional parameters, ϕ_i and π_i . The term ϕ_i is the probability of a mammography claim being captured in the HCCD among screening eligible women receiving government funded health insurance and was assumed to be perfect ($\phi_i=1$). On the other hand, the term π_i is probability of a mammography claim being captured in the HCCD among screening eligible women *not* receiving government funded health insurance and is derived from a Uniform distribution bound between (0, 0.6). We posited that π_i cannot exceed DHIN's assumption that 60% of the population is covered by the DHIN, because that assumption is based on a mix of all insurers, while we now are focused solely on non-government and self-payers. The proportion c_i can be described the Beta distribution with the shape parameters ($G_i + 1, N_i - G_i + 1$), where G_i is the number of women aged 40 and older receiving government funded health insurance in the i^{th} census tract obtained from the 2019 American Community Survey 5-year estimates tables B27003.

For example, if all the population in a census tract were on government funded health insurance ($c_i = 1$), then η_i also equals one, and no adjustment is necessary to the HCCD claims data for that tract. If none of the population were on government funded health insurance ($c_i = 0$), then the coverage of the HCCD may range from 0% to 60% in that tract and more aggressive adjustment is necessary. In a more realistic situation, suppose 40% of the population in a census tract were on government funded health insurance, then we would expect between 0% to 60% of the remaining 60% of the population to be underreported to the HCCD, with η_i ranging from $1*0.4 + 0*0.6 = 0.40$ to $1*0.4 + 0.6*0.6 = 0.76$.

Statistical analysis

We used descriptive statistics and choropleth maps to explore how mammography rates and breast cancer diagnoses were distributed spatially throughout Delaware. These statistics and maps were stratified by HCCD data years of 2019 (eAppendix) and 2022 (main text).

To calculate how mammography uptake related to breast cancer diagnoses, we fit a series of simultaneous autoregression (SAR) models, as we hypothesized that both mammography uptake and breast cancer diagnoses were spatially autocorrelated with each other given the administrative definition of census tracts. More specifically, we used spatial error linear regression models that estimated the effect of mammography uptake on breast cancer diagnoses and any uncaptured effect (error) of neighboring census tracts, weighting each tract by the population of women aged 40 or greater. Neighbors were defined using Queen's contiguity. Each analysis included SAR models for the observed apparent HCCD measure of mammography uptake and the misclassification-adjusted estimates stratified by total, local, and late breast cancer cases. We did not perform additional confounder adjustment as these are predictive ecological models.

We performed these analyses using a quantitative bias analysis (QBA) framework implemented via a probabilistic (Monte-Carlo) simulation. 10,000 simulations were run on the observed HCCD data to create the distribution of plausible counts of screening mammograms in Delaware accounting for underreporting, as well as the SAR models. We

added a constraint on both specifications of sensitivity so that the realized values must be greater than or equal to the observed prevalence and less than or equal to 1; this is to guard against implausible values occurring during the simulation, which is a known problem in probabilistic QBA.⁹ *A priori*, we did not have reason to believe either the DHIN-specification or the Census-specification would be preferred, thus we averaged the misclassified-adjusted mammography counts from both approaches for each census tract. The fixed effect of mammography uptake on breast cancer diagnoses from each SAR model was sampled from a Gaussian distribution informed from the point estimate and standard errors of the beta coefficient. Estimates correspond to the median and 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles (simulation intervals) of the posterior distribution of counts of screening mammograms and the SAR models fixed effects. All analyses were conducted in R version 4.1.0 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria). Analytic codes are available for download from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17342478>; however, HCCD data approved for this analysis are propriety and not publicly available.

Results

Mammography uptake

During the year 2022 and based on the HCCD observed measure, there were 47,906 screening mammograms in Delaware, a statewide averaged uptake of 176 mammograms per 1,000 women aged 40 and above. This exhibited heterogeneity by census tract, as

depicted in Figure 1, with a minimum of 76 and a maximum of 270 mammograms per 1,000 women aged 40 and above.

As expected, accounting for imperfect sensitivity boosted these counts. The statewide uptake increased to a median of 234 mammograms per 1,000 women (95% simulation interval: 230, 239). As compared to the observed measure, this resulted in a statewide difference of 58 mammograms per 1,000 women (95% simulation interval: 54, 63). Figures 2 maps the median census tract values for the misclassified-adjusted estimates.

Across the simulations, the DHIN-specification of sensitivity was high with a median of 96% across all census tracts in the State (range: 76%, 100%), while the Census-specification of sensitivity was lower with a median of 65% (range: 38%, 99%) (Figure 3). Correlation of sensitivities for the adjustment approaches (DHIN-specification and Census-specification) was 27%, suggesting that each specification contributed different information towards the final adjustment where the greatest amount of adjustment occurred via the Census-specification. Figure 4 is a Blant-Altman plot depicting the agreement between the two specifications: agreement diverged proportional to the number of mammograms in a census tract.

Breast cancer diagnoses

Between 2012 through 2021, there were 8,610 newly diagnosed invasive breast cancer cases in Delaware; by cancer stage, 5,852 local and 2,758 late. Figure 5

demonstrates the heterogeneity in cancer diagnoses by tract and Table 1 summarizes the results from the regression models.

Based on the observed measure of mammography uptake for 2022, each additional 1,000 mammograms was associated with an increase of 126 breast cancer cases (95% confidence interval: 112, 140), accounting for spatial dependency between census tracts and weighted by population. Stratified by local and late cases, each additional 1,000 mammograms was associated with an increase of 90 local breast cancer cases (95% confidence interval: 78, 101) and an increase of 37 late breast cancer cases (95% confidence interval: 31, 43).

When adjusting for presumed undercounting, each additional 1,000 mammograms was associated with a median increase of 77 total breast cancer cases (95% simulation interval: 63, 90), 55 local breast cancer cases (95% simulation interval: 45, 65), and 22 late breast cancer cases (95% simulation interval: 17, 27). Compared to the observed measure, this was a respective change of -39%, -39%, and -40% for total, local, and late cases.

Discussion

In this paper, we demonstrate how QBA may be used to address systematic error (misclassification) in the ascertainment of screening mammography uptake in a population using insurance claims data. While the true number of screening mammograms in a census tract were unobservable, we believe that the adjusted counts represent an improved estimate. Indeed, in the predictive models we observed a stronger ecological

association between total breast cancer cases and the number of screening mammograms as compared to late – i.e., more advanced – breast cancer cases and greater screening mammography. The overall attenuation of the estimates in Table 1 from observed to adjusted may be explained by increasing the number of screening mammograms per tract while holding the number of cancer cases constant.

These findings partly recapitulate what has been reported in the literature as increasing rates of screening mammography uptake are not always associated with improved early detection. Comparing the observed to the adjusted SAR models (Table 1), the adjusted model is closer to the null for the late cases. A study across all counties in the U.S. conducted in 2015 observed that “a 10–percentage point increase in screening [was] associated with increased incidence of early disease and no change in the incidence of locally advanced and metastatic disease.”¹⁰ A similar analysis conducted among U.S. female veterans from 2018 observed the same ecological association, whereby higher screening mammography rates leads to higher breast cancer incidence while also acknowledging that underreporting is a problem and work is needed to improve measures of mammography participation at a population-level.¹¹ Extending these findings, a Germany study that evaluated the impact of an organized mammography screening program designed to reach the 10 years after implementation found in initial increase in incidence, particularly for early-stage disease, followed by a reduction in later-stage disease and breast cancer mortality.¹²

Our group has found that both screening history and tumor aggressiveness independently predict stage at diagnosis.⁶ Geographic areas that have lower rates of

screening uptake and higher rates of more aggressive tumors were more likely to be identified as hotspots for advanced disease. A combination of genomics (i.e., a higher rate of a particular shared ancestry) and neighborhood exposures (e.g., air quality, food environment, reproductive behaviors, alcohol use, etc.) may contribute to higher rates of more aggressive disease.

The National Institutes of Health's National Cancer Institute (NCI) estimates that 73.7% of women aged 40 and over have received screening mammograms in the past two years as of 2022.¹³ It is difficult to compare these figures to our adjusted uptake because we were examining only single, nonconsecutive years of mammography uptake (2019 and 2022). If we assume a symmetrical distribution based on the NCI data, this suggests an annualized uptake of about 37% of the eligible population. Our statewide uptake post-adjustment was a median of 234 mammograms per 1,000 women aged 40 and above (95% simulation interval: 230, 239) as compared to the HCCD observed statewide averaged uptake of 176 mammograms per 1,000 women. In other words, we observed an adjusted uptake of 23% among the eligible population in Delaware versus the NCI estimate of 37%, a difference of 14 percentage points. However, the NCI data arise from BRFSS and are known to be overestimated for reasons provided in the Introduction.^{1,2} Regardless, we believe there is room for improvement in screening mammography uptake in Delaware.

There are many stakeholders interested in quantifying the uptake of screening mammography, as well as other preventive care procedures, at the population level including healthcare systems, public health and other government departments, and insurance companies.¹⁴ In addition to state insurance claims databases as used in our

work, third-party claims databases are a source of preventive care procedures across a broad geography. These databases may also be subject to misclassification though. While not specific to mammography, Dahlen et al. validated the Merative MarketScan database for the most common 250 inpatient procedures and found an averaged 28.5% underestimation of procedures (imperfect sensitivity).¹⁵ This underestimation exhibited patterns by neighborhood deprivation: high neighborhood deprivation led to higher underestimation whereas areas of low deprivation had an overestimation problem (imperfect specificity). The authors concluded that commercially insured patients were less likely to have inpatient procedures than noncommercial patients and third-party insurance databases that include commercial patients are more likely to have imperfect sensitivity because they are underestimating the noncommercial insurance procedures. This may be explained as by the assertion that commercial insurance underestimates procedures since procedures are more common in older patients covered by Medicare. The HCCD, on the other hand had imperfect sensitivity due to incomplete commercial plan coverage. Thus, it is essential to understand the catchment of aggregated healthcare databases to understand the mechanism of misclassification.¹⁶

We acknowledge several limitations along with strengths of our work. First, we lacked a more detailed breakdown of insurance types at the tract level and assumed misclassification was homogenous by insurance subtype. This assumption could be violated if, for example, a major self-insured employer who was not mandated to report claims data to DHIN provides a disproportionate share of employment to residents in an area. This would reduce the percentage of residents with commercial insurance in that

area who were included in the HCCD dataset relative to other areas where residents with commercial insurance were more likely to be employed by businesses or organizations that provided insurance with a mandate for claims reporting to DHIN. This could, in turn, complicate our assumptions regarding the insurance breakdown for the residents in each census tract who were not in the HCCD dataset. One way to possibly address this would be to obtain the aggregated counts of claims by insurance subtype, which was not available to us. Second, we had no way to assess the accuracy of address information in the HCCD. We were aware that certain census tracts were more likely to contain erroneous address information, whether proxy addresses or post office boxes as opposed to the patients' home addresses. This could result in spatial misclassification.¹⁷ We applied constraints to guard against impossible values generated during the QBA. Third, we were limited by nonconsecutive years for mammography data, which could potentially misclassify people as not having screening, which would further lower sensitivity. Fourth and finally, the sensitivity values were best guesses based on available data, whether DHIN or Census, and could be further improved with more informative priors, if such priors can be elucidated.

In terms of strengths, the use of a QBA framework provided a systematic approach for dealing with misclassification. We present a generalizable strategy for working with underreported population health measures and can be used by other jurisdictions for other preventive care procedures, such as uptake of screening colonoscopy. Additionally, partnering with DHIN helped us refine our procedure and bring important context to

nuanced problems that may otherwise be unknown to investigators, such as the spatial misclassification noted earlier.

In summary, when working with administrative datasets for measuring the uptake of screening mammography in a population, researchers and healthcare administrators should account for potential underreporting. We demonstrate how QBA can be used to address misclassification at a census tract level in Delaware, thereby improving quality of inference from the adjusted data. Ideally, we would recommend this be done near real-time, integrated into surveillance systems. In the meantime, there is still room to improve both the uptake of screening mammography across Delaware as well as continue to promote QBA methods when working with administrative claims data.

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Table 1. Results of the simultaneous autoregression models predicting incident breast cancer cases by uptake of mammography for census tracts in the State of Delaware. Breast cancer cases were diagnosed between 2012 and 2021. Mammography uptake was measured via the Delaware Health Information Network (DHIN) Health Care Claims Database for 2022. Uptake was analyzed as the observed measure presuming misclassification as well as the misclassified adjusted method.

Mammography measurement	Breast cancer cases		
	<i>Estimate (95% confidence/simulation interval)</i>		
	Total	Local	Late
Observed	126 ^a (112, 140)	90 (78, 101)	37 (31, 43)
Adjusted ^b	77 (63, 90)	55 (45, 65)	22 (17, 27)

^a Estimates may be interpreted as the averaged change in breast cancer cases for each 1,000 additional mammograms, accounting for spatial dependency between census tracts and weighted by population.

^b Adjustment based on 10,000 Monte-Carlo simulations. See text for details.

Figure 1. Screening mammography uptake per 1,000 women aged 40 and above by census tract for the State of Delaware. Mammography uptake was measured via the Delaware Health Information Network (DHIN) Health Care Claims Database for 2022 and are presumed underreported.

Figure 2. Screening mammography uptake per 1,000 women aged 40 and above by census tract for the State of Delaware. Mammography uptake was measured via the Delaware Health Information Network (DHIN) Health Care Claims Database for 2022, adjusted for presumed underreporting, and depicts the medians of 10,000 Monte-Carlo simulations. See text for details.

Figure 3. Histogram of sensitivities based on the DHIN-specification (γ) and Census-specification (η) adjustment methods. Values derived from 10,000 Monte-Carlo simulations adjusting observed mammography uptake measured via the Delaware Health Information Network (DHIN) Health Care Claims Database for 2022. See text for details.

Figure 4. Blant-Altman plot for agreement between the DHIN-specification and Census-specification adjustment methods. Each point represents a census tract in Delaware, the y-axis is the difference between the two specifications, and the x-axis is the average of the two specifications. The solid line represents the average difference in measurements between the two specifications, while the dashed lines represent the 95% confidence interval limits for the average difference. Values derived from the median of the 10,000 Monte-Carlo simulations adjusting observed mammography uptake measured via the Delaware Health Information Network (DHIN) Health Care Claims Database for 2022. See text for details.

Figure 5. Incident breast cancer diagnoses per 1,000 women aged 40 and above between 2012 and 2021 by census tract for the State of Delaware.

